

Changes in Household Structure and Consumption Patterns among Households with HIV-positive members in Uttar Dinajpur district, West Bengal

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Abstract: The HIV/AIDS epidemic threatens the social shape of the most affected international locations. Of all the units suffering from the HIV/AIDS epidemic, people, households, and families are the most affected. Evidence shows that the AIDS epidemic has severe consequences on households. In addition to the social and psychological outcomes, HIV contamination poses a serious hazard to the household economy. The HIV/AIDS epidemic can result in an exchange within the composition of families, with the gradual disappearance of parental technology and kids cared for with the aid of grandparents and other households some cases, older kids may additionally act as surrogate dads and moms for his or her younger siblings, main to an increase in single-era households headed by older kids. The composition of many families is complex and changes through the years. It is even greater complex when the head of the household, generally a person, will become inflamed with HIV, will become ill and in lots of cases dies. This also results in moving dynamics inside households. There are some ways in which HIV and AIDS can have an effect on the extent and sample of household consumption and in the end, have a negative impact on character sectors. The analysis suggests that families with HIV participants spend a big part of their monthly intake expenditure on medicines. Nearly 12.53 percent of the whole consumption expenditure of families with HIV is dedicated to scientific fees at the submit-symptomatic level which is a good deal better than the expenditure on education. This confirms the general idea within the literature that HIV and AIDS can affect kids' schooling. As nutritious and balanced meals are vital to ensure longer and healthier lives for human beings living with HIV/AIDS (PLHA), it's far critical to decide whether those families spend less on food, or not, even in absolute phrases, inside the post-symptomatic stage. The policy reaction has to encompass the proper stability among targeted medical health insurance interventions and social security structures to protect households with HIV+ individuals from impoverishment because of HIV-associated illnesses.

Keywords: HIV/AIDS, consumption pattern, HIV-infected families, household composition

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1. Introduction:

According to the latest available estimates, about 2.5 million people are currently living with HIV or AIDS in India, corresponding to an HIV prevalence rate of 0.36 percent in the population aged 15–49 years (IIPS 2007). The HIV/AIDS epidemic threatens the social structure of the most affected countries. Of all the gadgets tormented by the HIV/AIDS epidemic, individuals, families, and households are the most affected. Proof indicates that the AIDS epidemic has critical effects on households. The impact on the household starts off evolved as soon as a member suffers from HIV-associated ailments. In addition to social and psychological results, 3 kinds of monetary effects may be outstanding. The primary is the loss of earnings of a family member, especially if he is the breadwinner. The second effect is a growth in household expenditure to cowl the cost of treatment. A 3rd impact is the oblique charges resulting from own family members being absent from paintings or school to take care of an AIDS-affected person.

Figure 1 illustrates the processes by which HIV-related illness or the death of one of its members from AIDS affects the household economically and socially:

Fig: 1 Conceptual Framework of the Socio-Economic Impact of the HIV/AIDS epidemic on households

Source: "Impact of AIDS", United Nations Secretariat, Population Division

In addition to the economic impact that the HIV/AIDS epidemic can have on households and families, it can also have social impacts. The household is the first unit of socialization and can undergo enormous changes. The death of an adult may lead to dislocation or dissolution of the household, and children may be sent to live with relatives. Some children may drop out of school not only because of financial constraints but also because no one is there to look after them. The number of female-headed impoverished households increases when the male breadwinner either suffers or dies of AIDS. Several studies have been conducted to find out the impacts of people living with HIV, but no studies have been reported in the Uttar Dinajpur district of West Bengal. The household impact study below was conducted to examine changes in household composition and the social consequences.

2. Sample size, sampling process, and data collection

This is a study that used a quantitative approach to collect information. A personal interview was conducted to obtain information from respondents. A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. A total of 93 respondents were approached to participate in the survey (which included about 50 households from different blocks of the district). The source of information for the survey was people living with HIV/AIDS (PLHA) aged 18 and above who had been diagnosed as HIV positive more than a month or year before the survey. A purposive sampling method was used to select participants for easy recruitment and active participation of respondents in the research.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Profile of the respondents:

Out of the total 93 respondents, 47 percent were men and 53 percent were women. Of these, 69 percent were between the ages of 25 and 40. About 60.2 percent of respondents were Muslim. Almost 37 percent of women and 32 percent of men were illiterate respondents. 72 percent of respondents used Anti-Retroviral Therapy (ART).

Table-1: socio-economic characteristics of the respondent

Characteristics	No. of Respondents
Gender	
Male	44 (47)
Female	49 (53)
Age Group of Respondent	
18-25	29 (31)
26-40	64 (69)
Educational Status	
Illiterate	32 (34)
Primary	33 (36)

Secondary	21 (23)
Higher-Secondary	7 (8)
Main Occupation	
Non-Agricultural wage Labour	23 (25)
Truck driver	7 (7)
Agricultural Wage Labour	13 (14)
Business	8 (9)
Cultivator	1 (1)
Local Driver	7 (8)
Housewife	19 (20)
Housemaid	8 (9)
Service	2 (2)
Not able to work	5 (5)
Having ART or NOT	
Having ART	67 (72)
Not Having ART	26 (28)

Source: Field data (figure in parenthesis indicates percentage)

Income of Households (Annual Income): Total respondent HHs- 50	
Up to Rs. 24000	19 (38)
Rs. 24001-Rs. 48000	19 (38)
Rs. 48001- Rs. 72000	7 (14)
Rs. 72000 and above	5 (10)

Source: Field data (figure in parenthesis indicates percentage)

3.2 Change in the composition and structure of households as a result of the disease:

The purpose of this section is to analyze whether the composition of the household has changed after one or more household members became ill. It compares household composition in two phases: pre- and post-symptomatic.

The "pre-symptomatic" phase refers to the period when all members of a given household are from medically free health problems and are therefore able to function well. The "post symptomatic" phase can be divided into two: pre-and post-diagnosis, in each of which one or more household members experienced HIV-related symptoms, although they were unaware of their positive status until properly diagnosed. The loss of a breadwinner obviously tends to reduce the economic viability of the household that remains, and some households faced with this situation may disintegrate, with members dispersing to the households of relatives.

Table 2(A): HIV and AIDS affected households' socio-demographic characteristics:

Household Composition	Pre-Symptomatic (%)		Post-Symptomatic (%)	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Live with Parents/in-laws	36 (82)	41(84)	2(5)	4(8)
Nuclear	8(18)	8(16)	42(95)	45(92)

Source: Field Data (figure in parenthesis indicates percentage)

Table 2(B): Composition of Households

Pre-Symptomatic Phase	
Composition of Nuclear family	composed of one to three children, ranging in age from 6 to 14 years.
Composition of Parental family	composed of one or two children under 12

Post Symptomatic Phase	
Composition	The number of single-parent households had increased from one to four
	Four (4) women reported that their husbands had died from HIV/AIDS-related illnesses or that they had separated, leaving them with at least one or two dependents who had gone to live in parental households.

Based on data from all 93 participants, during the pre-symptomatic phase, 16 lived in nuclear households (one or two parents with children), almost composed of two adults with one to three children aged 6 to 14 years. Of these 16 nuclear households, 14 had children under the age of 14 who were dependent on their parents, while another five contained at least one child aged 14+ who worked part-time (more common for sons) or did housework. and acted as caregivers to their parents (more common in daughters).

During the post-diagnosis phase (at the time of the interviews), the majority of respondents who had previously lived with their parents/in-laws had moved into a nuclear family (87 out of 93). However, the number of single-parent households increased from one to four, with four women reporting that their husbands had died of HIV/AIDS-related illnesses or had separated, leaving at least one dependent aged 12 or younger.

In addition, four participants who lived with their in-laws during the pre-symptomatic phase returned to their own parents after their husbands died of an HIV-related illness. Only 2 (two) men continued to live there with their parents after being diagnosed with HIV, and a total of 6 respondents reported living with their paternal families at the post-diagnosis stage, four women and two men.

During the post-diagnosis phase, 10 women reported becoming head of their household, with four becoming single parents, four heading a household in which their husband was still alive but very ill, and two continuing to live with their parents after their death. Their spouse, but not as a dependent. In addition, two women who became single parents went to live in paternal households where their mothers were already head of households, the women became heads of their changed households, either because they were widowed or separated from their husbands and chose to live alone or only with their children under 14 years of age. (See Fig. 2(a) and (b)).

Fig: 2(a) and (b): Household Composition (pre- and post-diagnosis phase)

The composition of many households is complex and changes through the years. It's far even more complex whilst the head of the household, normally a person will become inflamed with HIV, turns unwell, and in many instances dies. This also ends in transferring dynamics within households.

The electricity to mobilize sources typically rests in the arms of the head of the household. In this study, it becomes located that the identification of the "family head" varied. Contributors generally take into consideration themselves as head of their family once they have been the only earner or earned more than any other household member. A few (especially ladies) became the top in their families while their husbands left them after being recognized with HIV. However, in a few instances, the participant had a dominant presence within the family, main different contributors to view them as the top. Examples of each are given below:

A 39-yr Hindu married guy diagnosed in 2007 lived together with his wife, daughter, mom, and younger brother in a residence given to his mom after his father died. His mother and more youthful brother lived off his father's pension. While asked who, he considers to be the pinnacle of his

household, he replied, "...my spouse works as a field employee in UDP+ and earns Rs. 5000 in keeping with month. The cash I earn Rs.1200, is not enough to hold our family jogging. My spouse is the pinnacle of the family, she earns more than me and supports us. ..." as a consequence, he considered his spouse as the pinnacle of the household due to the fact she became the main earner, despite the fact that he earned little cash and his mother acquired a pension.

Average, changing family power dynamics, manifested amongst other matters inside the identification of the pinnacle, might be anticipated to persuade the mobilization and use of cloth and social resources, however little extra records is available because own family participants apart from the studies respondents were no longer interviewed. This bankruptcy will consequently be based totally on an evaluation of the approaches wherein livelihoods have changed based on the statements of the interviewed members – all of whom have been HIV advantageous but had unique positions in their households.

3.3 Change in household consumption pattern due to illness:

There are a number of approaches in which HIV and AIDS can affect the level and sample of household intake and in the long run have a detrimental effect on person sectors. The evaluation shows that households with HIV contributors spend a massive part of their monthly intake expenditure on drug treatments. Kids' training expenses make up a smaller part of the total monthly fees. A high share of clinical costs impacts the economic scenario of households with HIV participants.

Table 3: Share of expenditure on some major items:

Items	Pre-Symptomatic phase (%)	Post-Symptomatic phase (%)
Cereals	15.35	12.66
Pulses	2.62	2.43
Other Food	31.77	29.66
Total Food	49.74	44.75
Fuel and Light	8.15	7.76
House Rent	1.34	2.63
Clothing	5.69	4.84
Education for Children	3.86	3.05
Medical	3.58	12.53
Durables	2.22	1.32
Other Non-Food	25.42	23.12
Total Non-Food	50.26	55.25

Source: Field data

Within the sample, almost 12.53 percentage of the total intake expenditure of households with HIV is devoted to scientific costs within the publish-symptomatic level. Concerning children's education, it is able to be visible that HIV families spend a smaller part of their overall consumption expenditure on training at the put-up-symptomatic level. This confirms the overall concept inside the literature that HIV and AIDS can affect kids' training. As nutritious and balanced foods are important to make certain longer and healthier lives for humans dwelling with HIV/AIDS (PLHA), it is far essential to decide whether or not these families spend less on food, even in absolute terms, in the post-symptomatic level.

For example, the average direct cost to an HIV-affected household at the last visit to a treatment center was found to be Rs 609, which was 20.3% of the average household income (Rs 3,000). The average treatment cost (cost of drugs in case of opportunistic infection) for HIV/AIDS at the last visit was Rs 372, which was 61% of the average direct cost at the last visit. Transportation costs accounted for 17% of average direct costs. Patient food costs were close to about 10% of average direct costs. Thus, the total cost of treatment and access of PLHIV at the last visit was Rs 535, which is 87.8% of the average direct cost of the last visit. The cost of accompanying persons was 12.2% of the average direct cost (Rs. 74).

The study found that households with HIV+ members spent a large proportion of their total expenditure on food and medical care. It highlights their economic situation and draws attention to impoverishment due to health expenditure. Children's education bills for an insufficient share of general intake expenditure in families with HIV+ members, indicating how HIV/AIDS influences kid's education and hinders the formation of future human capital (Pradhan et al., 2006).

4. Conclusion:

The economic burden of HIV-related illnesses on the family degree is embodied in fitness expenditure, main to multiplied poverty amongst households with HIV+ participants. Infection-associated healthcare expenses disproportionately influence families beneath the poverty line (Kamolratanakul et al., 1999). The maximum extreme impact of HIV/AIDS become felt at the household stage. The contamination or dying of a household member manner a reduction or lack of family income, a drop in productiveness, and a massive lack of family financial savings because of scientific, care, and funeral prices. The effect of HIV/AIDS is generally amazing on negative families, which might be least organized to cope with such issues. By its very nature, AIDS can kill a couple of family member, as spouses or partners and children can also be infected, adding to the economic and psychological burden on households. The overall properly-being of surviving household

contributors declines due to economic hardship, infection, and grief over the loss of a relative. In some cases, the family breakdowns.

Therefore, the monetary burden of disease associated with HIV contamination is a severe problem for health policymakers. In the absence of social aid applications and health insurance for people dwelling with HIV, that is sufficient to push a few households underneath the poverty line. Families with HIV+ individuals need plenty more support from the authorities in terms of getting the right of entry to and affordability of health care to keep away from financial disaster. The coverage response needs to include the ideal stability among centered medical insurance interventions and social safety structures to defend households with HIV+ individuals from impoverishment because of HIV-related ailments.

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